

MADICES

Machine-Actionable Data Interoperability for the Chemical Sciences (MADICES)

Electronic Lab Notebook Interoperability
MADICES 3 Report

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Event Description

This was the third iteration of the MADICES Workshop. The key aims of MADICES are to address critical challenges in making scientific data, workflows, and software interoperable and reusable across different platforms in the chemical sciences. MADICES 3 brought together experts from a range of different backgrounds and projects to advance interoperability, open science and FAIR principles across the chemical sciences.

Event Sponsors

Event Data & Materials

All of the code and working group discussions produced as part of MADICES 3 can be found in our [GitHub Repository](#).

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1 Summary

Electronic Laboratory Notebooks (ELNs) are increasingly central to scientific research, offering digital environments for recording, managing, and sharing experimental data [1]. However, the diversity of ELN platforms [2] and their underlying data models presents significant challenges for interoperability, hindering collaboration, reproducibility, and long-term data stewardship.

This report provides a comprehensive overview of ELN interoperability, synthesizing insights from the MADICES 2022, 2024 and 2025 workshops. It explores the technical and semantic barriers to data exchange across ELNs and outlines emerging strategies to overcome them.

Key topics include:

- The fragmentation of ELN platforms and its impact on collaborative workflows
- The role of structured formats like JSON, JSON-LD, and RO-Crate in enabling data portability
- Use cases for backup, migration, collaboration, and integration with external systems
- Challenges such as semantic annotation gaps, complex data structures, and instrument integration
- Mechanisms including the .eln File Format, RO-Crate Schema Plus, and API-based exchange
- Recommendations for standardization, semantic mapping, and demonstrator development

The report aims to guide researchers, developers, and data managers in adopting interoperable ELN practices that support FAIR data principles and scalable scientific collaboration.

2 Background

ELN interoperability refers to the ability of Electronic Laboratory Notebooks to exchange, interpret, and reuse data across different platforms, institutions, and workflows. This capability is essential for enabling collaborative research, ensuring reproducibility, and supporting long-term data stewardship in line with FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable) [3] data principles.

ELN interoperability is valuable in a wide variety of ways. It has the potential to facilitate seamless data exchange across diverse ELN systems and to enable integration with broader research infrastructure through open standards and APIs. It can offer support for both structured and unstructured data, including metadata and annotations, while simultaneously mitigating the risks of vendor lock-in and promoting long-term data accessibility. Further benefits can arise from greater reproducibility and regulatory compliance in digital research workflows.

However, achieving interoperability presents several challenges: **(i) Platform diversity:** Institutions often use multiple ELNs with incompatible data models; **(ii) Semantic gaps:** Lack of standardized metadata and ontologies hinders meaningful data exchange; **(iii) Technical limitations:** Incomplete import/export capabilities and inconsistent APIs; **(iv) Workflow complexity:** Differences in sample-centric vs. process-centric data handling; and **(v) Integration barriers:** Difficulty linking ELNs with instruments, LIMS, and automation tools

The [MADICES](#) (Metadata and Data Interoperability in Chemical and Engineering Sciences) workshops have served as a collaborative platform for exploring these challenges and opportunities. Since 2022, participants have explored foundational issues, practical tooling, and domain-specific use cases to advance ELN interoperability across the scientific landscape.

2.1 MADICES 2022

At the [2022 MADICES workshop](#), participants explored the diversity of ELN platforms in use across institutions and disciplines, and the implications this has for data sharing and collaborative research. Key themes included:

- The need for ELNs to support both structured and unstructured data, including metadata, annotations, and experimental context
- Concerns about long-term data accessibility and the risk of vendor lock-in, especially with proprietary systems
- The importance of open standards and APIs to enable integration with other research infrastructure
- The role of ELNs in supporting reproducibility, regulatory compliance, and digital research workflows
- The trade-offs between commercial and open-source ELNs, including cost, support, and flexibility

A significant portion of the discussion also focused on the use of [JSON](#) as a flexible and widely adopted format for structuring ELN data. JSON's compatibility with web technologies and its human-readable syntax were seen as advantages for both developers and researchers. However, concerns were raised about the lack of semantic richness in raw JSON exports, which can hinder interoperability across systems.

To address this, the [RO-Crate](#) (Research Object Crate) format was proposed as a promising solution. RO-Crate builds on [JSON-LD](#) (JSON Linked Data) to provide a structured, machine-readable way to describe research data and its metadata. Participants discussed how RO-Crate could serve as a bridge between ELNs and other digital research infrastructure, enabling more consistent and meaningful data exchange. The potential for RO-Crate to support modular profiles tailored to different scientific domains was also highlighted.

2.2 MADICES 2024

The [2024 MADICES Workshop](#) expanded the conversation to focus on interoperability between [ELNs and samples](#), particularly around sample-centric and process-centric workflows. Participants emphasized the importance of capturing sample history and state transitions in a way that supports both experimental and computational data. Key insights included:

- The need to annotate samples with metadata that distinguishes between mutable and immutable attributes, and to track sample transformations over time.
- Recognition of different workflow philosophies: sample-centric (where data accumulates on a single sample entity) versus process-centric (where each transformation creates a new sample instance).
- The importance of graph-based representations (e.g., using [RO-Crate](#) and [JSON-LD](#)) to flexibly model relationships between samples, processes, and measurements.

- Suggestions for linking to out-of-band data, e.g., stored in LIMS (Laboratory Information Management System) or automation tools, while maintaining a coherent archive through metadata annotations and access descriptors.
- Discussions around stateful sample modeling, where a permanent sample object is paired with a state object to reflect current conditions, enabling both traceability and modularity.

The workshop also explored [platform-agnostic interoperability](#), advocating for standards that allow ELNs to exchange data regardless of vendor or system architecture. This included:

- Emphasizing the use of IRIS and Semantic Web principles [4] to support distributed data referencing.
- Highlighting the importance of self-describing data packages that can be parsed and understood without prior knowledge of the originating system.
- Proposing a shift from bespoke platform-specific APIs to a unified delivery interface per platform, capable of receiving semantically annotated "crates" (e.g. RO-Crate packages) and unpacking them using standardized tooling.
- Supporting the use of [RDF](#), particularly JSON-LD serialization, to ensure semantic consistency and compatibility with existing specifications like RO-Crate and the [.eln File Format](#).
- Encouraging the development of demonstrators and working groups to test and extend these concepts, including integration with metadata extractors and registries such as those developed by [MaRDA](#) and [MaterialDigital](#) [5].

3 MADICES 2025

Building on the foundational themes of 2022 and the workflow-focused discussions of 2024, the [2025 MADICES Workshop](#) concentrated on two core areas: Detailed use cases for ELN Interoperability, and considering these use cases with respect to the existing challenges and wider mechanisms for semantic interoperability and the current suitability of the [.eln File Format](#) to support these cases. These investigations culminated in some recommendations for approaches, and considerations of future directions of this work.

3.1 Use Cases for ELN Interoperability

The MADICES 3 workshop reviewed a comprehensive set of ELN interoperability scenarios, and created formal use cases for them, grouped by theme. Each use case includes its goal, summary, example, pre-conditions, data considerations, and commentary on [.eln File Format](#) suitability.

3.1.1 Data Preservation

These use cases focus on ensuring ELN data can be reliably backed up and restored.

Use Case Name: Singular ELN Backup & Restore

- **Goal:** Enable users to recover their ELN data within the same system.
- **Summary:** Supports round-trip data recovery for individual users.
- **Example:** A researcher backs up their ELN and restores it after a system update.

- **Preconditions:** Same ELN instance; user account remains the same or is reassigned.
- **Data considerations:** Experiment records, metadata, dependencies, account details, sharing permissions.
- **ELN File Format suitability and commentary:** We would expect this to be supported - Round Trip should be viable (.eln can store arbitrary PropertyValues).

Use Case Name: Whole ELN Backup & Restore

- **Goal:** Restore an entire ELN ecosystem.
- **Summary:** Complex restoration involving multiple users and embedded structures.
- **Example:** An institution restores a full ELN instance after a server migration, or some form of data loss/failure.
- **Preconditions:** Same ELN instance; consistent user and group structures.
- **Data considerations:** User accounts, experiments, metadata, dependencies, templates.
- **ELN File Format suitability and commentary:** Not currently suitable, and perhaps not required to be. Native support or standardization may be more realistic.

3.1.2 Data Migration

These use cases address the transfer of ELN data between systems.

Use Case Name: Singular ELN Migration

- **Goal:** Transfer a user's ELN data to a different ELN.
- **Summary:** Requires semantic mapping and metadata translation.
- **Example:** A researcher moves their ELN data to a new institution's platform.
- **Preconditions:** Both ELNs support .eln format and semantic mapping.
- **Data considerations:** Experiment records, metadata, dependencies, account details, sharing permissions. Some data is no longer relevant, e.g., institutional data.
- **ELN File Format suitability and commentary:** Potentially viable. Would need the mapping for the metadata/semantic annotation - being addressed by the [RO-Crate Schema Plus](#).

Use Case Name: Multiple ELN Migration

- **Goal:** Migrate an entire ELN ecosystem to a new platform.
- **Summary:** Institutional-level migration with complex data structures.
- **Example:** An organization (e.g., a University) transitions from one ELN system to another.
- **Preconditions:** Both ELNs support .eln format and semantic mapping. New ELN must support similar structures (e.g., groups and inventories), full import/export of .eln format. Potentially custom parsers/API functionality.
- **Data considerations:** User accounts, groups, experiments, inventories, templates.
- **ELN File Format suitability and commentary:** Not currently suitable. Would need the mapping for the metadata/semantic annotation - being addressed by the [RO-Crate Schema Plus](#).

3.1.3 Collaboration and Publishing

These use cases support sharing ELN data across different researchers and organizations, and preserving ELN data for future use and collaboration.

Use Case Name: ELN Collaboration

- **Goal:** Enable cross-platform collaboration between researchers via data sharing.
- **Summary:** Sharing and integrating experiments across different ELNs.
- **Example:** Two labs using different ELNs collaborate on a joint study.
- **Preconditions:** Both ELNs support .eln format and semantic mapping.
- **Data considerations:** Experiments, metadata.
- **ELN File Format suitability and commentary:** Depends on support. Would need the mapping for the metadata/semantic annotation - being addressed by the RO-Crate Schema Plus. Or more general RO-Crate / .eln Profiles, e.g. using [OO-LD \[6\]](#).

Use Case Name: ELN Archiving and Publishing

- **Goal:** Archive ELN data for future reuse or publication.
- **Summary:** Supports long-term preservation and accessibility.
- **Example:** A researcher publishes archived ELN data alongside a journal article.
- **Preconditions:** ELN supports .eln format and semantic mapping.
- **Data considerations:** Experiments, metadata.
- **ELN File Format suitability and commentary:** .eln export recommended.

3.1.4 Integration with External Systems

These use cases focus on connecting ELNs with other tools and instruments.

Use Case Name: Exchange ELN Data with Other Systems

- **Goal:** Use ELN data in external processing systems.
- **Summary:** Requires interoperability with workflow engines and archives.
- **Example:** ELN data is used as input for a simulation pipeline.
- **Preconditions:** ELN and External system must support .eln data formats.
- **Data considerations:** Experiments, metadata.
- **ELN File Format suitability and commentary:** .eln lacks domain-specific metadata transfer, RO-Crate Schema Plus could be suitable.

Use Case Name: Instrument Workflow Integration

- **Goal:** Integrate instrument-generated data into ELNs.
- **Summary:** Automate data ingestion from instruments.

- **Example:** A microscope sends measurement data directly to an ELN.
- **Preconditions:** API compatibility; semantic annotation; instrument generates .eln (or RO-Crate) and ELN can import .eln.
- **Data considerations:** Data files, metadata.
- **ELN File Format suitability and commentary:** Not currently specified. Requires API and semantic compatibility.

3.2 Challenges in Achieving Interoperability

Achieving seamless ELN interoperability is complex and multifaceted. It requires addressing technical, semantic, and organizational barriers that affect how data is structured, annotated, exchanged, and reused across systems. These challenges are compounded by the diversity of ELN platforms, the evolving nature of scientific workflows, and the need for scalable, sustainable solutions.

Recent studies have explored these challenges in depth. For example, Higgins et al. [7] provided a review exploring the factors that should be considered when introducing electronic laboratory notebooks in academic environments, highlighting the importance of context-specific requirements and institutional support. The [ELNdataBridge](#) project [8] demonstrates a novel API-based solution for interoperability between the [Chemotion ELN](#) and [Herbie](#), showcasing the potential for semantic data exchange in chemistry and materials science.

Some of the specific challenges that may be encountered during ELN integration include:

- **Diverse data models:** ELNs vary in how they structure experiments, samples, and metadata, making consistent data exchange difficult.
- **Semantic annotation gaps:** Not all ELNs support ontologies or semantic schemas, limiting the ability to interpret and reuse data.
- **Export/Import limitations:** Round-trip data exchange is often incomplete or lossy, especially when metadata is not preserved.
- **Link rot and external dependencies:** Referencing external ontologies or resources can lead to broken links and outdated references. However, incorporating entire ontology files can lead to bloated, over-sized files.
- **Complex data structures:** Nested and interlinked data objects are difficult to flatten and represent in standardized formats.
- **Instrument integration:** Manual data handling from instruments is inefficient and error-prone, and integration often requires custom solutions.
- **Ownership and access control:** Managing permissions and ownership during data export/import adds complexity, especially across institutional boundaries.
- **Scalability and performance:** Large ontologies and datasets can slow down processing and validation, requiring optimization strategies.
- **User burden:** Without automation and intuitive tools, users may struggle to curate, annotate, and share data effectively.

3.3 Mechanisms and Approaches

Efforts such as [RO-Crate](#), [RO-Crate Schema Plus](#), and the [.eln File Format](#) created by the ELN Consortium, as well as integration frameworks like [SILA](#) and [FINALES](#) [9], aim to address these challenges by providing standardized mechanisms for data packaging, semantic annotation, and instrument integration and automation. FINALES acts as a message broker for coordinating communication in large-scale scientific projects, while SILA provides a framework for the exchange, integration, sharing, and retrieval of electronic laboratory information.

3.3.1 RO-Crate and RO-Crate Schema Plus

Ro-Crate provides a lightweight, JSON-LD-based format for packaging research data with metadata. The Schema Plus extension enhances semantic annotation and supports ELN-specific use cases. Discussions emphasized the need to flatten nested structures and include ontology files directly in the crate to avoid link rot.

3.3.2 Ontologies and SHACL

Using modular ontologies and SHACL shapes allows for validation and semantic consistency. However, large ontologies can be slow and unwieldy. Modularization and selective inclusion were proposed to improve usability.

3.3.3 API-Based Data Exchange

Electronic Lab Notebooks like [elabFTW](#) demonstrate how APIs can be used to iteratively request and resolve linked data. The use of machine-actionable links and self-describing data was highlighted as essential for scalable interoperability.

3.3.4 Instrument Integration Standards

[SILA](#) and [FINALES](#) offer frameworks for integrating instruments with ELNs. SILA enables direct interaction without middleware, while FINALES supports brokered communication. Combining both could support cross-lab collaboration and repeatable integration patterns.

4 Recommendations and Future Direction

Based on the collective insights from the MADICES workshops and broader community practices, the following recommendations aim to aid in the future success of ELN interoperability in scientific domains.

- **Standardize export formats:** Promote adoption of RO-Crate, RO-Crate Plus, and .eln profiles across ELNs.
- **Develop semantic mappings:** Agree on shared ontologies and schemas for metadata. Avoid passing internal ELN-specific data that lacks external meaning.
- **Automate instrument workflows:** Use standards like SILA to streamline data flow. Instruments should be able to send RO-Crates directly to ELNs with minimal manual steps.
- **Create demonstrators:** Build proof-of-concept integrations to validate approaches. Examples include ingesting RO-Crates into platforms like [OpenBIS](#) or [DataLab](#).

- **Support API-driven interoperability:** Ensure ELNs expose sufficient API endpoints for data access and manipulation. Consider access levels and ownership logic at import/export stages.
- **Enable self-describing data:** Use semantic annotations and indexing algorithms to help systems follow relevant links and resolve references automatically.

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